

Full Length Article

Green ammonia production in Denmark: Assessing future potentials and challenges

Hossein Asgharian^{a,*}, Henrik Lund^b, Jakob Zinck Thellufsen^b, Florin Iov^a, Mads Pagh Nielsen^a, Vincenzo Liso^a

^a Department of AAU Energy, Aalborg University, Pontoppidanstræde 111 9220 Aalborg, Denmark

^b Department of Sustainability and Planning, Rendsburggade 14, Aalborg University, Denmark

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Blue Ammonia Production
Green Ammonia Production
EnergyPLAN
CO₂ emissions
Renewable Energy Sources

ABSTRACT

Ammonia stands as one of the most critical chemical products, finding extensive applications across various industries. Currently, its production relies heavily on fossil fuels, leading to the depletion of fossil fuel resources and significant CO₂ emissions. While ammonia is primarily used as a fertilizer in agricultural sectors, its potential as a valuable carbon-free fuel has attracted significant interest in shipping and energy industries. This has led to anticipation of increased ammonia production in the future, primarily through green and carbon-free methods. However, transitioning from the conventional blue ammonia production method, which relies on fossil fuels, to green ammonia production presents considerable challenges and necessitates thorough evaluations. This study compared the impacts of green and blue ammonia production on Denmark's energy system in 2030 and 2045. It was revealed that green ammonia production entails higher investment costs due to the utilization of electrolyzers for hydrogen production, which are powered by wind turbines. Additionally, it contributes to increased investment and fixed operating costs of the energy system, as a considerably larger number of wind turbines are required for green ammonia production. However, the study's findings indicated that green ammonia production can potentially be more cost-effective than blue ammonia production, especially in 2045 when equipped with hydrogen storage. This cost-effectiveness primarily stems from projected decreases in the costs of electrolyzers and hydrogen storage vessels by 2045, as well as the omission of carbon capture and storage (CCS) from the system, along with substantial savings in fuel costs. Thus, the study demonstrated that opting for green ammonia production over blue ammonia generation could lead to a decrease in required additional annual costs by 11.4% and 40% in 2030 and 2045, respectively.

1. Introduction

Ammonia is a vital chemical with numerous applications. While widely utilized as a fertilizer in agriculture, its utility extends beyond fertilizer production. Specifically, ammonia serves as an environmentally valuable refrigerant, extensively employed in industries for vapor compression refrigeration cycles and absorption cooling system [1]. Additionally, ammonia possesses exceptional thermophysical properties. Unlike Hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs), it has no adverse impact on the ozone layer. Therefore, it is commonly used in ice factories and cold storage facilities [2]. Furthermore, ammonia can also be utilized as a fuel within combustion engines and fuel cells. Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs), popular for their exceedingly high efficiency in power generation, can utilize ammonia as fuel for power generation [3]. In this

case, the utilization of ammonia as a fuel in SOFC can be considered highly advantageous. This is not only due to the very high energy density of ammonia but also because it is a carbon-free fuel with zero CO₂ emissions. Additionally, ammonia is not only cheaper than hydrogen but also has a higher volumetric energy density than hydrogen, which is comparable to gasoline [4]. Furthermore, the production of ammonia is not challenging; it can be conveniently handled and distributed without requiring additional infrastructure, making it economically feasible. Ammonia can be utilized in diverse combustion systems and holds great potential to replace fossil fuels such as gasoline, kerosene, and diesel [5]. However, despite all the aforementioned advantages of using ammonia as a fuel, it should be noted that ammonia possesses a very high ignition temperature and an exceedingly slow flame speed [6]. Additionally, studies have shown that water and nitrogen are not the only products of

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: hoas@energy.aau.dk (H. Asgharian).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2025.134423>

Received 24 July 2024; Received in revised form 14 January 2025; Accepted 15 January 2025

Available online 21 January 2025

0016-2361/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

ammonia combustion. In other words, ammonia combustion may result in the emission of NO_x , especially when combustion occurs at high temperatures and pressures [7]. Even though mixing ammonia with other fuels can address challenges such as very high ignition temperatures and slow flame speeds, further research in the field of ammonia combustion is needed to overcome these obstacles completely.

Ammonia is primarily generated in three forms: grey, blue, and green. Gray ammonia represents the production of ammonia using fossil fuels, typically through methods such as steam methane reforming (SMR). This production method not only depletes fossil fuel resources but also emits a significant amount of CO_2 directly and indirectly. According to [8] CO_2 emissions from gray ammonia production plants vary depending on the feedstock, methods used, and the age of the plant. For instance, an ammonia production plant that consumes natural gas for hydrogen production emits around 1.8 tons of CO_2 per ton of generated ammonia. However, this figure increases to higher values, up to 3.2 tons of CO_2 per ton of ammonia, when using coal for hydrogen production. When the CO_2 produced during the hydrogen generation via the SMR process is captured using a CO_2 capture and storage (CCS) technology, the resulting hydrogen derived from fossil fuels but with lower CO_2 emissions can be used to produce blue ammonia. While establishing a gray ammonia synthesis plant requires lower investment costs and has lower operational costs compared to the blue ammonia production option, it may not be considered very cost-effective when CO_2 taxes are high. Studies have shown that gray ammonia produced by SMR becomes economically viable when the CO_2 tax does not exceed \$62 per ton [9]. Capturing the CO_2 emitted from the SMR plant during ammonia production results in the generation of a more environmentally friendly ammonia product with lower environmental impacts. However, establishing a blue ammonia production plant may require higher initial investment costs and higher operational costs. The integration of a CCS plant with the SMR process is evaluated by Khan et al. [10]. In this study, it was reported that natural gas costs predominantly determine the operating costs of hydrogen production using the SMR process, while the integration of CCS significantly increases capital costs. Proniewicz et al. [11] conducted a life cycle assessment on various ammonia production methods. Their findings revealed that grey ammonia contributes the highest CO_2 emissions, whereas pink ammonia, derived from a nuclear plant with water electrolysis, exhibits the lowest CO_2 emissions. Furthermore, the study demonstrated that although ammonia production methods based on nuclear and renewable energy sources (RES) are favorable concerning human health and climate change, they indicate unfavorable impacts on ecosystems and freshwater.

Green ammonia production indeed represents a promising pathway towards decarbonizing the ammonia industry. This ammonia production method, unlike gray and blue methods, operates independently of fossil fuels and has zero CO_2 emission. Instead, it harnesses renewable energy sources such as wind and photovoltaics to power electrolyzers that generate hydrogen. This hydrogen then combines with nitrogen, primarily sourced from cryogenic air separation units (CASUs), to produce green ammonia. Notably, energy-efficient reactors are employed in green ammonia production to reduce the need for installing RES with exceptionally high capacities. In this case, Smith et al. [12] opted for a ruthenium-based catalyst over an iron-based one due to its heightened activity at lower pressures. Additionally, they proposed employing an integrated reactor incorporating both catalyst and sorbent material to absorb and separate ammonia from unreacted gases. This setup enables surpassing single-pass equilibrium limitations. Palys et al. [13] developed a dynamic model to assess decentralized ammonia production plants powered by wind turbines with capacities ranging from 100 kg/h to 10,000 kg/h. In this study, they used MgCl_2 as sorbent materials for ammonia separation. Ishaq et al. [14] also developed transient models to assess the utilization of offshore wind energy for green ammonia production. In this study, they considered hydrogen storage to enable continuous green ammonia generation. The economic findings highlighted that offshore wind turbines and electrolyzers are the primary

cost drivers. Vinardell et al. [15] also conducted an assessment of green ammonia production in Spain, contrasting it with grey ammonia production utilizing natural gas and SMR. The findings revealed that while green ammonia production can significantly mitigate environmental impacts and opting for it may prevent ozone depletion and reduce reliance on fossil fuels. Nonetheless, choosing green ammonia production may also lead to heightened land use, mineral resource scarcity, freshwater eutrophication, and land acidification. Furthermore, the study demonstrated that green ammonia production could become economically feasible when governments impose high CO_2 tax.

The EnergyPLAN model operates at high speed, allowing it to conduct comprehensive simulations across all energy sectors, including heating, electricity, and transportation, in just a matter of seconds [16]. This tool is primarily utilized to assess future system designs when RES hold a significant share in power generation. Since 1999, it has been instrumental in the development of several hundred research papers [17]. Ferrari et al. [18] evaluated various planning tools suitable for analyzing cities, capable of assessing energy services, technologies, and generating detailed reports conveniently. In this study, they analyzed 17 planning tools and identified energyPRO, iHOGA, HOMER, WebOpt, SIREN, and EnergyPLAN as user-friendly options. These tools are highly proficient in conducting hourly energy calculations and have the potential for broad utilization. Pastore et al. [19] employed the EnergyPLAN software to compare and assess various small-scale power-to-x strategies within renewable energy communities. The study findings suggested that power-to-gas emerges as a reliable strategy, particularly with a significant share of RES in power generation. Nevertheless, it was noted that it may not be the optimal choice due to the substantial investment costs associated with electrolyzers.

This study, for the first time, compares the generation of blue and green ammonia in the future of Denmark for the years 2030 and 2045 using the EnergyPLAN software tool. It calculates the ammonia production capacity based on government reports for those years and assesses the changes in CO_2 emissions, investment costs, and annual costs when transitioning from blue to green ammonia. Additionally, the study determines the required increase in RES capacity to establish green and blue ammonia production plants without increasing CO_2 emissions within the energy sector. Furthermore, this study evaluates the impact of hydrogen storage on both the annual investment costs and the additional annual costs associated with green ammonia production in the years 2030 and 2045.

2. Model description

Ammonia is generated through an exothermic reaction in which four moles of reactants are converted into two moles of ammonia, as shown in reaction (1). In this case, according to Equation (2), 177 kg of hydrogen should react with 823 kg of nitrogen to yield 1 ton of ammonia.

According to [20] Denmark is set to establish a 1.01 GW hydrogen production plant for green ammonia production by 2025. In this context, we assumed the utilization of alkaline electrolyzers for this purpose, with an initial investment cost of €550/kW in 2030, according to Danish technology catalog [21]. This study assumes that Denmark will maintain this level of ammonia production by 2030. Estimations of annual ammonia production capacity rely on the assumption that a 2 MW electrolyzer can produce hydrogen at a rate of 38 kg/h [22]. Consequently, the projected output of the 1.01 GW hydrogen production unit stands at 0.168 million metric tons (Mt) of hydrogen annually for ammonia synthesis. In this case, the calculated power consumption for water electrolysis (8.8476 TWh/year) is added to the electricity demand

Fig. 1. Simplified process flow diagram for green ammonia production process (Comp; Compressor, Div; flow divider, HX; heat exchanger, HPC; high pressure column, Cond; condenser, Mix; mixer, F; flash, LPC; low pressure column, Reb; reboiler, AEL; alkaline electrolyser, R; reactor, EV; expansion valve). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

in EnergyPLAN, while the electrolyser investment costs (555.5 M€) are included under the additional costs in the investment and fixed operating and maintenance tab considering 2 % for the fixed operating and maintenance costs. EnergyPLAN initially meets the added power demand by increasing fossil fuel consumption in the energy sector, which leads to higher CO₂ emissions unless the capacity of renewable energy systems is increased. According to Equation (2), the conversion of the produced hydrogen into green ammonia requires 0.782 Mt of nitrogen, resulting in an anticipated annual ammonia yield of 0.9497 Mt. This study assumes that the required nitrogen is locally supplied using a cryogenic air separation unit (CASU). To convert the generated nitrogen and green hydrogen into green ammonia, this study explores a modified Haber-Bosch (HB) process, a novel and energy-efficient method for sustainable and green ammonia production. Utilizing MgCl₂ or CaCl₂ as sorbent material for ammonia absorption and separation, it eliminates the need for a chiller in the separation process. Furthermore, unlike the conventional HB process, which operates at elevated pressures (150–200 bars), this method operates at significantly lower pressures (20 bars), synthesizing ammonia at 400 °C and separating it from unreacted gases at 200 °C through absorption. Despite being in the early stages of development, with a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 4–5, this ammonia production method exhibits noticeably higher energy efficiency than the conventional HB process. The simplified process flow diagram for green ammonia production is shown in Fig. 1. In this process, deionized water and air, the main feedstocks, are used to generate green ammonia. As illustrated, dried air (state 1) enters the CASU, where it is pressurized to 6.5 bar and then water-cooled (state 3). A flow divider then splits this stream into two: the stream with a higher flow rate enters directly into the multi-stream heat exchanger, while the lower flow rate stream is further pressurized, water-cooled (state 7), and then directed to the multi-stream heat exchanger. Both streams are cooled to

extremely low temperatures, around −166 °C (states 8 and 10). The liquefied air (state 8) is expanded through an expansion valve before entering the low-pressure column (LPC), which operates at 1.2 bar. Meanwhile, the primary air flow (state 10) is introduced to the high-pressure column (HPC), operating at 5 bars. From the top of this column, a nitrogen-rich stream (state 11) exits and enters a condenser that supplies heat to the LPC's reboiler. This nitrogen stream is then divided, with one portion recycled back to the HPC (state 14) and the main liquefied nitrogen stream expanded and directed to the LPC. Within the LPC, product streams of nitrogen and oxygen (states 22 and 25) are generated, along with a waste stream (state 17). These cold streams pass through the multi-stream heat exchanger to cool the incoming air. The waste stream, primarily nitrogen and oxygen, is discharged to the atmosphere (state 18), while the oxygen stream is pressurized (state 24) and stored in a tank. The nitrogen stream, the intended product of the CASU, is compressed (state 27) and mixed with pressurized green hydrogen (state 30) from the water electrolysis process.

The nitrogen and hydrogen gas mixture (state 32) are preheated before entering the modified green Haber-Bosch process (state 33). In this process, the mixture passes through an ammonia synthesis reactor, and the produced ammonia is separated from the gas mixture using a sorbent bed. After several cycles of ammonia synthesis and separation, the unreacted nitrogen and hydrogen gases are pressurized, reheated, and recycled to mix with the fresh feed (state 33) before reentering the reactor. For simplicity, the ammonia desorption process that yields ammonia is not shown in Fig. 1.

To compare green and blue ammonia production in Denmark's future, this study evaluated both processes at equal capacity to assess their impacts on Denmark's energy sector in 2030 and 2045. Hence, in the case of blue ammonia production, steam methane reforming (SMR) is utilized to generate the necessary hydrogen, using natural gas and

Fig. 2. Simplified process flow diagram for blue ammonia production (Comp; Compressor, HX: heat exchanger, Cond: condenser, Mix: mixer, F: flash, Reb: reboiler, EV: expansion valve, HT-WGS: high temperature water gas shift, LT-WGS: low temperature water gas shift, PSA: pressure swing adsorption, Evap: evaporator). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

steam. While this method does not demand a high amount of electric power for hydrogen generation, it results in both the depletion of fossil fuel resources and the emission of a significant amount of CO_2 . In this case, according to [23] 4.5 Nm^3 of natural gas is needed to produce 1 kg of hydrogen through SMR. Additionally, the production of 1 kg of hydrogen using this method emits 8.76 kg of CO_2 [24]. In addition to natural gas and steam, the SMR process requires electricity to compress the reactants, as the reformer operates at elevated pressures to enable pressure swing adsorption for separating the generated hydrogen from CO , CO_2 , H_2O , and CH_4 . The blue ammonia production process employs the conventional Haber-Bosch process, which operates at elevated temperature and pressure, utilizing chillers to condense ammonia and separate it from the unreacted gases. Although this technology is mature and possesses a TRL of 9, it is highly energy intensive.

This study employs an amine-based process, recognized as the most mature post-combustion CO_2 capture technology, to capture CO_2 emitted by point sources within the energy sector and the SMR process for producing blue ammonia. This study does not consider the fluctuations in the energy penalty of the CCS technology with varying CO_2 concentrations within the flue gas emitted from SMR and other point sources. Consequently, it considers a constant value for the energy penalty of the CCS when integrated with various point sources. Fig. 2 indicates a simplified process flow diagram of blue ammonia production. Steam (state 10) and natural gas (state 9) are introduced to the reformer to produce syngas (state 13). Syngas production is an endothermic reaction that occurs at elevated temperatures (above 800°C), with heat typically supplied by the combustion of natural gas. In this process, as can be seen, high- and low-temperature water-gas shift reactions convert carbon monoxide and steam into CO_2 and hydrogen. Consequently, the gas mixture exiting the low-temperature water-gas shift reactor (state 15) consists primarily of CO_2 and H_2 , with trace

amounts of CH_4 , H_2O , and CO , which then enter the pressure swing adsorption to separate the hydrogen content. The CO_2 -rich stream (state 16) is combined with flue gas from the combustion of natural gas (state 12) and then enters an amine-based process (state 34) to capture CO_2 , while the separated hydrogen stream with high purity (state 17) is pressurized and mixed with pressurized nitrogen (state 5) from CASU. This mixture is heated to elevated temperatures (state 20) before introduction to the conventional HB process. As shown in Fig. 2, in the HB process, the gas mixture enters the first reactor where nitrogen and hydrogen partially convert into ammonia (state 21) as the reaction reaches equilibrium, and the gas mixture's temperature rises due to the exothermic nature of the reaction. The mixture is then cooled and enters the second reactor (state 22) to further convert reactants into ammonia, increasing its concentration in the gas mixture (state 23). Subsequently, the gas mixture is cooled by heating the cold recycle stream of unreacted gases (state 27) and further cooled by a vapor compression refrigeration cycle to liquefy the generated ammonia. The cold stream of liquefied ammonia and unreacted gases (state 25) enters a flash tank, where high-purity liquefied ammonia exits from the bottom (state 26), while unreacted gases exit from the top. The unreacted gases are pressurized (state 29) and recycled to the reactor, where they are mixed with the fresh feed stream.

Appendix A summarizes the parameters utilized in EnergyPLAN for estimating the costs and energy consumption of various units involved in both green and blue ammonia production. It is worth noting that equation (3) was used to calculate the capital costs of the desired plant based on the capital costs and capacity of reference plants given in Appendix A [25].

$$C = C_{ref} \left(\frac{Cap}{Cap_{ref}} \right)^{\beta} \cdot \alpha \quad (3)$$

Table 1
Summary of key assumptions for modeling green and blue ammonia production plants in Denmark for 2030 and 2045.

Parameter	Assumed value
Hydrogen production capacity of a 2 MW electrolyser	38 kg/h
Electrolyser investment costs	€550/kW in 2030 €333.3 /kW in 2045
Operating and maintenance costs of green and blue ammonia production plants	2 % of initial investment costs
Required natural gas for production of 1 kg of hydrogen using the SMR	4.5 Nm ³
CO ₂ emissions for 1 kg hydrogen production using the SMR	8.76 kg
Lifespan of plants for green and blue ammonia production	25 years

where C , C_{ref} denote the capital investment cost of the desired plant and the reference plant, respectively. Additionally, Cap , Cap_{ref} represent the capacity of the desired plant and the capacity of the reference plant, respectively, where β is the scaling exponent with a value of 0.5 and α is the overall installation factor with a value of 1.

It is worth noting that this study assumes a 25-year lifespan for both blue and green ammonia production plants, with their equipment specified in Appendix A, and incorporates a 2 % of initial investment costs as fixed operating and maintenance expenses. Additionally, the study assumes that the energy penalty of the amine-based method, as a post-combustion CO₂ capture technology, will remain relatively stable in the future. Table 1 summarizes the assumptions used in modeling the green and blue ammonia production in Denmark for 2030 and 2045. Appendix B further outlines the key assumptions for calculating the operating and maintenance costs of primary components used in the reference models (energy sector and transportation of Denmark, excluding the CCS and ammonia production plants) for 2030 and 2045. It is worth noting that the wind power generation costs calculated in this study encompass all expenses, from turbines to transmission lines. The per-unit costs of onshore wind turbines, detailed in Appendix B, cover the turbine costs, installation and development costs, decommissioning costs of the existing turbines, grid connection costs, and land purchase costs for 2030 and 2045. Additionally, 1.25 % and 1.67 % of these costs are allocated for fixed operating and maintenance expenses in 2030 and 2045, respectively. This study increases the capacity of onshore wind turbines to meet the power demand for green and blue ammonia production due to its economic advantages. However, the reference model incorporates offshore wind turbines and photovoltaics as well. The per-unit costs of offshore wind turbines shown in Appendix B include expenses for installation, project development, array cables, foundations, grid connection, and turbines. Fixed operating and maintenance costs of

the offshore wind turbines account for 1.87 % and 2.51 % of these expenses in 2030 and 2045, respectively. Similarly, the per-unit costs of photovoltaics, also detailed in Appendix B, include the grid connection costs, inverters costs, photovoltaic modules costs, and installation costs, with the fixed operating and maintenance costs comprising 1.45 % and 1.5 % of these expenses in 2030 and 2045, respectively.

This study utilizes the existing EnergyPLAN models developed to illustrate the transition of the Danish energy system towards carbon neutrality by 2045 [26,27,28]. It compares the implications of generating gray, green, and blue ammonia in Denmark's future. The reference models for Denmark's future energy system in 2030 and 2045, which do not include the ammonia production, have already been validated in reference [26]. To validate these models, Denmark's energy system in 2020 was simulated using the EnergyPLAN, and the model results were compared with national statistics. As shown in Fig. 3, the results obtained from the EnergyPLAN model for 2020 are consistent with the national statistics for that year, as provided in reference [29], confirming the reliability of the EnergyPLAN model. Then, based on the results from the validated 2020 model, scenarios for Denmark's energy system in 2030 and 2045 were developed. In the 2030 reference model, where ammonia production is not considered, CO₂ emissions total 11.59 Mt, with 4.0162 Mt emitted by point sources within the energy sector and 7.536 Mt from transportation. However, in the 2045 reference model, CO₂ emissions within the energy sector and transportation are zero. This is primarily attributed to the extensive adoption of battery electric vehicles, plug-in hybrid vehicles, electric trains and buses for transportation, coupled with an energy system that relies heavily on RES facilitated by an integrated smart energy system.

It is worth noting that the EnergyPLAN tool used in this study can balance electricity, district heating, cooling, natural gas, and hydrogen on an hourly basis, taking into account contributions from water electrolysis, gasification, and biogas processes. The objective of EnergyPLAN in technical simulations is to reduce the fuel consumption by maximizing the utilization of renewable energy. The specific implementation depends on the chosen model; however, EnergyPLAN generally aims to minimize the excess electricity production by promoting cross-sectoral utilization while reducing power generation from conventional power plants. For more details, see reference [17]. From Lund et al. [17] the operation can be detailed as in Fig. 4. According to this figure, once all required data is entered into the EnergyPLAN model such as RES capacity, hourly RES distribution, heat supply, fuel allocation for various applications, electricity demand, and CO₂ emissions tax, EnergyPLAN begins by using variable RES and waste heat to meet the power and district heating demands. The model then identifies any flexible power demand entered by the user, allowing annual power demand for specific applications to be shifted daily, weekly, or monthly. This flexibility

Fig. 3. Comparison of 2020 EnergyPLAN model results with 2020 national statistics [29].

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the calculation process for modeling the energy systems in EnergyPLAN [17].

helps EnergyPLAN align power supply with demand more efficiently. Flexible demand must be kept below a maximum threshold, represented as Max-effect in EnergyPLAN. Then, the user can select the operational strategies for combined heat and power (CHP) units and heat pumps, optimizing them to minimize the electricity exports by prioritizing heat pumps and CHP. Next, EnergyPLAN uses hydropower to reduce surplus power generation from condensing-mode power plants, which can produce more electricity than needed. In this case, hydropower is primarily used to partially replace the electricity generated by condensing-mode power plants, reducing both critical excess electricity production (CEEP) and exportable excess electricity production (EEEP), with priority given to minimizing CEEP. EnergyPLAN can also reduce hydropower capacity in response to CEEP and use electricity storage to further lower the CEEP. In the following steps, EnergyPLAN models heat pumps, CHP, and heat storage. If heat storage is used, the model employs stored heat in power generation to balance supply and demand, updating individual CHP and heat pump outputs. The model then accounts for different types of electrolyzer systems which can be used to provide hydrogen for micro-CHP or other applications such as transportation or hydrogenation. EnergyPLAN next evaluates thermal storage in district heating systems to reduce excess and condensing-mode power generation. In the next calculation step, the model incorporates vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technology, enabling smart charging and discharging. The model accounts for the charging of electric vehicles during the periods of CEEP, while ensuring that the battery capacity stays within the grid limits. At this stage, the EnergyPLAN model assesses power storage options, such as batteries or other storage technologies, with the primary goal of

reducing the CEEP. In the final step of modeling the energy system with EnergyPLAN, measures to minimize the CEEP are implemented. Options for reducing the CEEP include decreasing variable RES capacity, reducing CHP production, replacing fuel-based boilers with electric heating, and expanding CO₂ hydrogenation [17].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Model for gray, blue and green ammonia production in 2030

This section describes the impact of gray, blue and green ammonia production technologies on Denmark's energy system in 2030. Fig. 5 illustrates how CO₂ emissions in Denmark increase with the addition of blue and green ammonia production plants to the reference model. It is evident that CO₂ emissions increase more significantly when producing blue ammonia, primarily due to the utilization of natural gas in the SMR process, which results in significant CO₂ emissions. Furthermore, when blue and green ammonia production are added to the reference model without increasing the capacity of RES, the EnergyPLAN model balances the demand for these plants by increasing fuel consumption in the energy system which contributes to noticeable CO₂ emissions.

Even though the green ammonia production process is fuel-independent, as shown in Fig. 5, its integration into the reference model leads to high CO₂ emissions. This is primarily attributed to the substantial power demand required for water electrolysis, leading to increased fuel consumption within the energy sector to balance the power demand in the ammonia production process, when the capacity of

Fig. 5. Variation in (a) fuel costs and CO₂ emission costs (b) annual investment costs, variable costs, fixed operation costs and total annual costs resulting from the addition of green and gray ammonia production plants to the reference model. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2
Comparison of increasing the capacity of onshore and offshore wind turbines for covering the ammonia production plants.

		Onshore	Offshore
Gray ammonia	Increase in capacity of wind turbine (%)	41.92	19.23
	CO ₂ emission costs (M€)	459	459
	Annual investment costs (M€)	14,802	14,824
	Fuel costs (M€)	3,544	3,546
	Total annual costs (M€)	22,554	22,599
Green ammonia	Increase in capacity of wind turbine (%)	103.96	47.21
	CO ₂ emission costs (M€)	401	401
	Annual investment costs (M€)	15,000	15,052
	Fuel costs (M€)	3,322	3,781
	Total annual costs (M€)	22,542	22,647

RES remains constant. Consequently, while maintaining the RES capacity for ammonia production may lead to savings in investment costs, it simultaneously increases CO₂ emissions, fuel expenses, and CO₂ tax or CO₂ emission costs. To calculate the CO₂ emission costs, EnergyPLAN model first computes the CO₂ emissions within the energy sector and industries. Subsequently, it calculates the total CO₂ emission costs using the CO₂ tax, which needs to be inputted as CO₂ price in EnergyPLAN model in euros per ton of CO₂ emitted. In this scenario, the CO₂ tax per ton of emitted CO₂ in 2030 and 2050 is 34.6 €/ton_{CO₂} and 46.6 €/ton_{CO₂}, respectively [30]. In this case, the CO₂ tax per ton of emitted CO₂ in 2045 was calculated using linear regression.

Fig. 5 also compares the annual investment costs, variable costs (fuel costs and CO₂ emission costs), fixed operation costs, and total annual costs of the system (reference model with the inclusion of gray and green ammonia production plants). It is evident that the annual investment

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. The impact of CCS on (a) on CO₂ emissions and its corresponding costs (b) variable costs and fixed operation costs (c) annual investment costs and total annual costs when producing green and blue ammonia. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

costs rise with the addition of ammonia production plants to the reference model. However, this parameter increases more significantly with green ammonia production, primarily due to the higher costs associated with alkaline electrolyzers. Variable costs, encompassing CO₂ emission costs, fuel expenses, electricity exchange costs, and marginal operation costs, experience a more substantial increase with the integration of green ammonia production into the reference model. This is mainly attributed to the increased electricity exchange costs within the energy sector when producing green ammonia. Total annual costs represent the

summation of variable costs, fixed operation costs, and annual investment costs, which, according to Fig. 5, escalate further with the addition of a green ammonia production plant to the reference model.

In fact, balancing the power requirements of green and gray ammonia production plants by increasing fuel consumption within the energy sector is not optimal, as it leads to significant CO₂ emissions. Therefore, prioritizing the expansion of RES capacity to fulfill the power demands for ammonia production is crucial. This could involve further increasing the capacity of onshore wind, offshore wind, and

Fig. 6. (continued).

photovoltaics (PV). While PV has contributed partially to power supply in the reference model in 2030, its capacity was not further expanded due to geographical constraints. Hence, this study focused on boosting onshore and offshore wind capacities for this purpose.

Table 2 illustrates the necessary increase in the capacity of onshore and offshore wind turbines in the reference model to meet the demands for the ammonia production plants. It is evident that the capacity of wind turbines needs to be expanded nearly 2.5 times more when producing green ammonia, primarily due to the heightened electricity demand for hydrogen production via water electrolysis. According to Table 2, when producing green ammonia, the annual investment costs would increase with higher rate when power is supplied by offshore. Hence, Table 2 underscores the cost-effectiveness of utilizing onshore wind turbines to meet the power demand in ammonia production plants. Despite the challenges posed by the substantial power requirements of generating green ammonia, its associated costs, including CO₂ emissions costs, fuel costs, and total annual expenses, would be lower due to its independence from fossil fuels. Green ammonia production has been evaluated in numerous studies, all of which highlight its high operational costs due to the significant electricity required to generate green hydrogen through water electrolysis. These studies primarily conducted techno-economic analyses using the grid-connected method, where power costs are calculated per MWh of consumed electricity. Consequently, the electricity costs for powering the electrolyzers remain high. In contrast, this study evaluates green ammonia production at a national scale using an off-grid method. Here, the electrolyzers are powered locally by wind turbines, eliminating the need for grid connection. While this approach increases the initial investment costs, it reduces the variable costs substantially. As shown in Table 2, this method requires substantial annual investment to establish the wind turbines necessary to power the electrolyzers. It is worth noting that green ammonia production becomes economically viable when powered by onshore wind turbines, as they provide a cost-effective energy source for electrolyzers. However, due to the relatively high land use requirements of onshore wind turbines, offshore wind turbines are often utilized to power the electrolyzers. This leads to higher investment and total annual costs of the system and as shown in Table 2, under these conditions, green ammonia production becomes economically unfeasible compared to

gray ammonia.

Additionally, to calculate the variable costs of green ammonia production, this study excludes the cost of deionized water, as it is negligible and has minimal impact on the overall green ammonia production costs [31].

Fig. 6 illustrates the impact of employing CCS on reducing the CO₂ emissions and its associated costs within both the energy sector and ammonia production plants. This figure also compares the annual investment costs, variable costs, CO₂ emission costs, fixed operating costs, and total annual costs for gray (with a CO₂ capture rate of zero), blue, and green ammonia production. When producing green ammonia, the CCS plant solely captures the CO₂ emitted by the energy sector, totaling 4.0162 Mt per year. However, in the case of generating blue ammonia, additional CO₂ needs to be captured and separated from SMR, alongside the emissions from point sources within the energy sector. Therefore, as illustrated in Fig. 6, CCS plays a more crucial role when capturing CO₂ from the system generating blue ammonia. Consequently, the utilization of the CCS plant in this scenario can effectively reduce the CO₂ emission costs. According to this figure, it is evident that variable costs decrease with the implementation of CCS, primarily due to the reduction in CO₂ emission costs. Fig. 6 highlights that variable costs decrease more effectively when employing CCS for blue ammonia production. In other words, the variable costs decrease by 1.78 % for green ammonia production and 2.33 % for blue ammonia production when 90 % of the emitted CO₂ is captured, due to an effective reduction in CO₂ emission costs. In this case, CCS can capture more CO₂, resulting in a greater reduction in CO₂ emission costs and, consequently, variable costs. This figure also highlights the difference in variable costs between green and blue ammonia production, largely attributed to the substantial natural gas consumption inherent in producing hydrogen through SMR for blue ammonia production. However, the utilization of the CCS leads to an increase in fixed operational costs. It is evident that the system incurs higher fixed operational costs when employing CCS at higher capacities. Fig. 6 also illustrates how annual investment costs and total annual costs fluctuate with the addition of the CCS to the system. It is apparent that annual investment costs rise when integrating CCS for capturing CO₂ from the SMR process (when generating blue ammonia) and energy sector. According to this figure, the annual investment costs increase by

Fig. 7. Variation of (a) required onshore wind capacity and (b) annual investment costs (c) total annual costs when using different strategies for hydrogen storage with different capacities.

0.9 % for green ammonia production and 1.3 % for blue ammonia production when capturing 90 % of CO₂ from the SMR process (in the case of blue ammonia) and the energy sector. As can be seen, the system incurs higher annual investment costs when generating green ammonia and utilizing CCS solely for capturing CO₂ from the energy sector. The disparity in annual investment costs between green and blue ammonia production methods primarily stems from the substantial investment required for onshore wind turbines and electrolyzers when generating green ammonia. While numerous studies have indicated that green ammonia production incurs higher operational costs due to the electricity required for green hydrogen production via water electrolysis (assuming power is sourced from the grid), this study suggests that green ammonia production actually involves lower operating costs but significantly higher initial investment costs. This issue is thoroughly addressed in reference [32], which evaluates green ammonia production at a national level in Morocco, highlighting that substantial initial investments are needed to establish the infrastructure for advanced renewable energy systems. This study also demonstrates that the cost of green ammonia production largely depends on the initial investment, primarily allocated to renewable energy systems. Despite the decrease in CO₂ emission costs resulting from the implementation of CCS, the total annual costs also increase with CCS adoption and capacity expansion,

leading to higher annual expenses. Despite the higher initial investment costs associated with establishing a green ammonia production plant due to the increased demand for wind turbines and the necessity of electrolyzers for hydrogen production, Fig. 6 suggests that the total annual costs of the system would be lower when producing green ammonia. This is mainly due to the significantly lower variable costs associated with green ammonia production, which emits no CO₂ during hydrogen production, and it is entirely independent of fossil fuels. These results are consistent with the reference [33], which calculated very low green ammonia production costs, as low as 285 €/ton, by 2050.

Hydrogen storage has the potential to lower the annual investment costs of green ammonia production by enhancing the utilization of intermittent RES. In this scenario, during the periods of abundant RES, particularly onshore wind, surplus hydrogen beyond the needs of the ammonia production process can be generated and stored in vessels. Consequently, when onshore wind resources are insufficient, the stored hydrogen can be used to fulfill a part or all of the hydrogen requirement for green ammonia production. However, following this approach requires additional alkaline electrolyzers to generate excess hydrogen during periods of abundant onshore wind. Furthermore, it entails the utilization of storage vessels, which adds to the initial investments. This study considers caverns as a potential solution for hydrogen storage,

Fig. 8. Comparing (a) additional annual costs to the reference model (b) annual investment costs of the system for blue and green ammonia production considering 10% higher and lower costs for CCS and ammonia production plant. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

with the costs sourced from the Danish technology catalog.

This study evaluates the impacts of hydrogen storage on the performance of green ammonia production plants and the energy sector, utilizing flexible demand options in the EnergyPLAN model. This study assumes that either a portion or the entire power needed for hydrogen production through water electrolysis can be flexibly distributed throughout the week, day or month based on the real electricity balance. To accomplish this, it is necessary to determine the Max-effect parameter in the EnergyPLAN model, which specifies the extent to which the capacity of electrolyzers with flexible demand can be augmented during periods of abundant onshore wind. This study assumed that the capacity of electrolyzers with flexible demand could be doubled during periods of abundant onshore wind and low electricity prices.

Fig. 7 illustrates that flexible demand for hydrogen production, enabled by hydrogen storage, enhances the efficient utilization of onshore wind power. With greater volumes of hydrogen storage, a reduced capacity of onshore wind turbines becomes adequate to meet

the power needs for green ammonia production. It is evident that the capacity of onshore wind turbines can be further diminished by freely distributing the demand of the electrolyzers over a month, offering more system flexibility. However, it requires significantly large hydrogen storage vessels. Consequently, as shown in this figure, this approach becomes less cost-effective when storing hydrogen at higher capacities. Moreover, Fig. 7 emphasizes that distributing the power demand of electrolyzers over a day does not lead to a noticeable reduction in onshore wind capacity; rather, it increases the investment costs of electrolyzers. This distribution strategy fails to reduce the annual investment costs of the energy sector integrated with the green ammonia production. As a result, the total annual costs as shown in Fig. 7 slightly increases when using this approach. According to this figure, it is evident that considering the flexible demand for electrolyzers over a week is the most economical approach. This occurs because it efficiently decreases the required capacity of onshore wind turbines by 15.3 % for continuous ammonia production without necessitating exceedingly

Fig. 9. The impact of adding green and gray ammonia production with variable capacity to the reference model on (a) CO₂ emissions and CO₂ emission costs (b) variable costs of the system. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 10. Additional onshore wind capacity and annual investment costs in energy sector for different capacities of green and gray ammonia production. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

large hydrogen storage vessels. Hence, this hydrogen storage method can effectively contribute to a reduction in annual investment costs by €42 million.

Fig. 8 compares the additional annual costs to the reference model as well as annual investment costs of the system for producing green and blue ammonia with a capacity of 0.949 Mt/year. It is important to highlight that the reference model does not include CCS or green/blue ammonia production plants. However, systems producing green or blue ammonia include CCS, which captures 90 % of CO₂ emissions within the energy sector and the ammonia production plant if blue ammonia is produced. As discussed in section 2, this study calculated initial investment costs based on the Danish technology catalog and the available literature. In this case, the costs of units used in the energy sector, as well as the costs of electrolyzers and hydrogen storage vessels taken from the Danish technology catalog, are projected for 2030. However, the costs of ammonia production plants, CASU, and CCS need to be projected for 2030. Therefore, this study assumes a potential 10 % increase or

decrease in the initial investment costs of these units by 2030 and evaluates the impact of these variations on the additional annual costs to the reference model, as well as the annual investment costs of the system, including the energy sector and ammonia production plants. As depicted in Fig. 8, a 10 % fluctuation in the initial investment costs of the above-mentioned components does not significantly impact the additional annual costs and annual investment costs of the system. Furthermore, despite the higher annual investment costs associated with the system generating green ammonia compared to the system producing blue ammonia, the additional annual costs to the reference model are 11.4 % lower when generating green ammonia. In other words, this figure suggests that producing green ammonia is more cost-effective than blue ammonia in 2030, as the total annual costs of the system generating green ammonia are closer to the reference model when compared with the system producing blue ammonia. This is primarily due to lower electrolyzer costs in 2030, reducing the required capacity of onshore wind turbines through 1-week flexible demand enabled by hydrogen storage, avoidance of extra CO₂ emissions in the ammonia production process, utilization of CCS with smaller capacities to capture CO₂ solely from the energy sector, and significant reduction in fuel costs, as the green ammonia production process is independent of natural gas and fossil fuels.

4. Model for gray, blue and green ammonia production in 2045

To reach zero emission targets by 2050, it is vital to increase ammonia production capacity in Denmark by 2045, as ammonia serves as a carbon-free fuel. Additionally, according to reference [34], global ammonia demand is expected to nearly double between 2030 and 2045. Hence, this study assumes that the capacity for ammonia production will increase by up to 100 % from 2030 to 2045 and compares the impacts of green and blue ammonia production on Denmark's energy system. Similar to Section 3.1, the impact of introducing fossil fuel-based ammonia (gray ammonia) production and green ammonia production into the reference model for 2045 is first evaluated. Then, the CCS is added to assess the effects of blue ammonia production on Denmark's energy sector in 2045. Fig. 9 compares the CO₂ emissions, CO₂ emission costs, and variable costs of the system when integrating green and gray ammonia production processes with the energy sector in 2045. It scales up the ammonia production capacity from 0.9497 Mt/year (the capacity in the 2030 model) to 1.899 Mt/year. Increasing the capacity of green and gray ammonia production plants without expanding the capacity of

Fig. 11. Variation of (a) CO₂ emissions and CO₂ emission costs (b) Variable costs and fixed operation costs of the system when producing green and gray ammonia with different capacities. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

RES results in an increase in fossil fuel consumption within the energy sector to meet the power demand of the ammonia production plants with higher capacity. This leads to elevated CO₂ emissions and, consequently, higher CO₂ emission costs as the capacity of the ammonia production plants grows. It is noteworthy that although the gray ammonia production process demands less power compared to the green ammonia generation method, primarily due to hydrogen production via natural gas in the SMR process. Fig. 9 also compares the variable costs of green and gray ammonia production. Notably, gray ammonia production demonstrates significantly higher variable costs across different

production capacities, primarily due to elevated fuel costs and increased CO₂ emission expenses, given its heavy reliance on fossil fuels.

As mentioned in section 3.1, balancing the power demand of ammonia production plants with fossil fuels within the energy sector is not the most optimal solution, as it results in very high CO₂ emissions, leading to elevated CO₂ emission costs and fuel expenses. Hence, it is of paramount importance to increase the capacity of RES to supply the required power for ammonia production processes, thereby mitigating extra fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions within the energy sector during ammonia production. Therefore, this study explores increasing

Fig. 12. (a) CO₂ emission and CO₂ emission costs (b) annual investment costs and fixed operating costs (c) variable costs and total annual costs of the system including the energy sector and blue ammonia production process when capturing up to 90% of CO₂ emissions. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the onshore wind capacity due to its economic viability to meet the demand for green and gray ammonia production plants with increased capacity. Fig. 10 illustrates the additional onshore wind capacity required to meet the power demands in both green and gray ammonia production processes when scaling up the ammonia production by up to two times from 2030 to 2045. As can be seen, generating green ammonia requires 1.62 times more onshore wind capacity compared to gray ammonia mainly due to the utilization of electrolyzers for hydrogen production, when the production capacity is 1.9 Mt/year. This leads to a notable increase in annual investment costs within the energy sector.

However, as shown in Fig. 11, green ammonia production powered by RES does not emit CO₂, resulting in substantial savings by eliminating CO₂ emission costs. Conversely, although the electricity required for gray ammonia is also sourced from onshore wind, it emits a large

amount of CO₂ due to utilization of SMR for hydrogen production, leading to significant CO₂ emission costs. According to Fig. 11, opting for green ammonia production not only saves costs by avoiding CO₂ emission expenses but also reduces fuel costs by eliminating the need for natural gas in hydrogen production. Thus, the variable costs for green ammonia production are considerably lower than those for gray ammonia production, as shown in Fig. 11. However, it indicates that the fixed operational costs in the system are higher when producing green ammonia, especially at higher production rates. This is primarily due to the installation of a substantially larger number of wind turbines, which entail higher operating and maintenance costs.

Fig. 12 illustrates the impacts of transitioning from gray to blue ammonia production with CCS, assuming an ammonia production capacity of 1.899 Mt/year and a CO₂ capture rate of up to 90%. As

Fig. 12. (continued).

mentioned before, the CCS is solely used to capture CO₂ emitted by the SMR process, as the energy sector and transportation system in Denmark in 2045 do not emit CO₂. Hence, in this study, a lower energy penalty for the CCS ($0.333 \frac{\text{MWh}}{\text{tonCO}_2}$) is considered, as it captures CO₂ solely from the SMR process, which is considered as a point source with a higher CO₂ concentration in [35,36]. As shown in Fig. 12, the CO₂ emissions and consequently the CO₂ emission costs reduce significantly, resulting in a 6.26 % decrease in variable costs with CCS implementation. However, integrating CCS into the blue ammonia production process results in additional investment costs as well as fixed operational costs, especially when establishing a CCS plant capable of capturing 90 % of CO₂ emissions. In this case, as shown in Fig. 12, annual investment costs may increase by 0.6 % when integrating CCS into fossil fuel-based ammonia production. Therefore, despite the substantial decrease in CO₂ emission costs with CCS, the total annual costs increase due to a significant rise in annual investment costs and fixed operational costs. It is worth noting that blue ammonia production in 2045 poses significant challenges, as amine-based processes are normally designed to capture up to 90 % of CO₂ emissions. Therefore, achieving CO₂ neutrality by 2050 would be very challenging when producing blue ammonia. Designing and implementing amine-based processes that can capture 100 % of CO₂ emissions may not be feasible, and even if feasible, the energy penalty of the CCS would increase significantly, making the process exceedingly energy-intensive.

Fig. 13 illustrates the impact of hydrogen storage on the performance of green ammonia production with a capacity of 1.899 Mt/year (twice the ammonia production capacity projected for 2030) when integrated into the energy system. It demonstrates that distributing the power demand of electrolyzers through hydrogen storage over a certain period (one day to one month) reduces the required capacity of onshore wind turbines for green ammonia production. Furthermore, extending the demand distribution over longer periods, such as a month, enhances the system flexibility, potentially further reducing the need for additional wind turbines. Table 3 indicates that the even though the annual investment costs may raise in 2030 with distributing the demand over 24 h, by 2045, these costs are expected to decrease when shifting the load over the same period, owing to the reduced costs of electrolyzers and hydrogen storage vessels in 2045. Even though adopting flexible

demand for electrolyzers over a month offers increased flexibility in the energy sector and potentially further reduces the need for onshore wind capacity compared to weekly demand distribution, it may not seem a feasible solution. In other words, this demand distribution requires very large hydrogen storage vessels. Hence, opting for this approach over flexible demand throughout a week may indeed decrease investment costs for wind turbines. However, it substantially adds to the investment costs for hydrogen storage. As shown in Fig. 13, at high hydrogen storage capacities, this approach is not very economically advantageous compared to shifting the load of electrolyzers over a week. According to this figure, the required capacity of wind turbines can be reduced by 33.3 %, leading to a 1.3 % reduction in annual investment costs when a one-week flexible demand is facilitated by hydrogen storage.

Fig. 14 also compares the additional annual costs to the reference model and the annual investment costs of the system when producing green and blue ammonia, factoring in a 20 % variation in the investment costs of CCS, CASU, and ammonia production plants. Table 4 highlights that the annual investment costs of the systems generating green and blue ammonia are closer in 2045 than in 2030, considering the variations in the investment costs of CCS, CASU, and ammonia production plants. Additionally, this comparison also indicates a more significant difference in additional annual costs to the reference model when producing green and blue ammonia in 2045. In other words, opting for green ammonia production results in reducing the additional annual costs to the reference model by 40 %. In this case, Fig. 14 highlights that in 2045, green ammonia production is significantly more cost-effective than blue ammonia production, as the total annual costs of the system producing green ammonia are substantially closer to the reference model compared to the system producing blue ammonia. Despite the consistent cost of natural gas at 8.3 €/GJ in 2030 and 2045 [30], the reduction in electrolyzer costs by 2045 (from €550/kW in 2030 to €333.3 /kW in 2045) and also avoiding the utilization of CCS when generating green ammonia resulted in a more noticeable difference between the additional annual costs to the reference model when producing green and blue ammonia in 2045. Fig. 14 further highlights that fluctuations in the investment costs of CCS, CCUS, and ammonia production plants do not significantly impact additional costs to the reference model and annual investment costs of the systems, particularly

Fig. 13. Variation of (a) required onshore wind capacity and (b) annual investment costs (c) total annual costs when using different strategies for hydrogen storage with different capacities.

Table 3

Comparing the annual investment costs of the systems generating green and blue ammonia with distributing the demand over 24 h in 2030 and 2045.

Ratio of stored hydrogen to produced hydrogen	Annual investment costs in 2030 for flexible demands over a day	Annual investment costs in 2045 for flexible demands over a day
0	15,138	18,277
0.1	15,139	18,270
0.2	15,141	18,263
0.3	15,142	18,250
0.4	15,142	18,239
0.5	15,142	18,230
0.6	15,142	18,222
0.7	15,143	18,212
0.8	15,143	18,204
0.9	15,143	18,194
1	15,145	18,188

concerning the system generating green ammonia. This is primarily attributed to the fact that in 2045, green ammonia production operates independently of CCS. Consequently, its annual investment costs are mainly driven by the costs of electrolysers and wind turbines, projected

to 2045 using the Danish technology catalog.

5. Conclusion

This study conducted a comprehensive assessment of Denmark's energy system when integrated with green and blue ammonia production plants. Utilizing data published by the Danish government, this study approximated the amount of ammonia production in Denmark for 2030 and thoroughly examined the impacts of green and blue ammonia production on the Danish energy system. The findings revealed that while opting for blue ammonia production may reduce investment costs and fixed operating costs in the energy sector due to decreased capacity requirements for onshore wind turbines, it substantially increases fuel costs and CO₂ emission costs, as it heavily relies on natural gas for hydrogen production via the SMR process. Additionally, higher capacities for the CCS are needed to capture CO₂ emissions when producing blue ammonia, adding to both investment and operating costs. Furthermore, the study indicated that employing CCS to capture up to 90% of CO₂ emissions from the energy sector and ammonia production processes (if producing blue ammonia) leads to a 0.9% increase in annual investment costs for green ammonia production and a 1.3% increase for blue ammonia synthesis in 2030. However, integration of

Fig. 14. Comparing (a) additional annual costs to the reference model (b) annual investment costs of the system for blue and green ammonia production considering 20% higher and lower costs for CCS and ammonia production plant. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 4
Annual Investment Costs Comparison for Systems generating Green and Blue Ammonia in 2030 and 2045 considering investment Cost Variations in CCS, CASU, and Production Plants.

		Annual investment costs of the systems (M€)	
		Green ammonia production	Blue ammonia production
2030	10 % higher costs	15,109	15,017
	Stable costs	15,095	14,997
	10 % lower costs	15,081	14,976
2045	20 % higher costs	18,057	18,035
	Stable costs	18,037	18,011
	20 % lower costs	18,017	17,987

CCS effectively reduces variable costs by 1.78 % and 2.33 % for green and blue ammonia production, respectively. The results of this study revealed that hydrogen storage, which assists in distributing the power demand of electrolyzers when producing green ammonia, can substantially reduce the need for additional wind turbines. This reduction leads

to decreased investment costs and fixed operating costs associated with green ammonia production. The study demonstrated that utilizing hydrogen storage to spread electrolyser demand over a week can decrease the required capacity for onshore wind turbines by 15.3 %, resulting in savings of €42 million in annual investment costs. Taking into account the lower costs of electrolyzers projected for 2030 (€550/kW), coupled with the flexibility in managing the power demand of electrolyzers enabled by hydrogen storage, and significant savings in natural gas expenses, it is estimated that the required additional annual costs for ammonia production could decrease by 11.4 % when opting for green ammonia production over the conventional blue ammonia synthesis method.

This study also investigated the impacts of green and blue ammonia production processes on Denmark’s energy system in 2045, considering the potential doubling of the ammonia production capacity from 2030 to 2045. It was shown that the utilization of CCS can increase the annual investment costs of the system by 0.6 %, while reducing the variable costs by 6.26 % due to a substantial reduction in CO₂ emission costs when generating blue ammonia with a capacity of 1.899 Mt/year. In contrast, green ammonia production results in no direct CO₂ emissions, as this production method operates independently of fossil fuels.

Moreover, the designed energy system in Denmark in 2045 relies entirely on RES and because of that there was no need for the integration of CCS into the system when producing green ammonia. It was also demonstrated that implementing 1-week flexible demand for electrolyzers, facilitated by hydrogen storage, could reduce the required capacity of onshore wind turbines and the annual investment costs of the system by 33.3 % and 1.3 %, respectively. This study concluded that the green ammonia production process, equipped with hydrogen storage, proves more cost-effective than blue ammonia production in 2045. This consideration takes into account the projected lower costs for alkaline electrolyzers (€337.5/kW) and hydrogen storage vessels in 2045, along with the avoidance of utilizing natural gas and CCS in the system. Consequently, the additional annual costs may decrease by 40 % when opting for a green ammonia production plant over a blue ammonia production system in 2045.

Although this study highlights the economic viability of producing green ammonia over blue ammonia in the future, implementing green ammonia production remains challenging. Achieving cost-effectiveness for green ammonia compared to blue ammonia production involves overcoming several obstacles. Primarily, this study assumes an expansion of onshore wind capacity to supply the necessary power for green ammonia production. In some cases, increasing the onshore wind turbine capacity may not be feasible due to their relatively high land-use requirements. In such scenarios, expanding offshore wind capacity would be necessary, which would raise the annual investment costs for green ammonia production beyond the values calculated in this study. This study also considers hydrogen storage in caverns, currently the most economical option. Yet, previous research indicates significant challenges with cavern storage, such as mechanical integrity, hydrogen loss due to halophilic bacteria, geochemical reactions, leaching issues, and potential hydrogen diffusion [37]. Thus, geological sites must be thoroughly evaluated to confirm their suitability for hydrogen storage.

Appendix A

Summary of parameters used for energy analysis and cost estimation of green and blue ammonia production in EnergyPLAN

Equipment	Specific investment costs/cost of reference plant	Capacity of reference plant	Power consumption
HB for green ammonia	1.317 M\$ [38]	$100 \frac{kg_{NH_3}}{h}$ [38]	$0.7 \frac{kWh}{kg_{NH_3}}$ [39]
Conventional HB process	2.957 M\$ [38]	$100 \frac{kg_{NH_3}}{h}$ [38]	$4 \frac{kWh}{kg_{NH_3}}$ [39]
Cryogenic air separation unit (CASU)	141 M\$ [25]	$52 \frac{kg_{O_2}}{s}$ [25]	$370 \frac{kWh}{ton_{N_2}}$ [40]
Steam methane reforming (SMR)	7321\$/kg/day [41]	$100 \frac{kg_{H_2}}{day}$ [41]	$0.1 \frac{kWh}{kg_{H_2}}$ [41]
CO ₂ capture and storage (CCS)	5.8 M€/ton _{CO₂} /h [42]	–	$0.383 \frac{MWh}{ton_{CO_2}}$ in 2030 [43]
Caverns for Hydrogen storage	0.00213 M€/MWh (2030) 0.0014 M€/MWh (2030) [21]	–	$0.333 \frac{MWh}{ton_{CO_2}}$ in 2045

Appendix B. Summary of investment costs, operating and maintenance costs and the expected lifetime used in the reference models in 2030 and 2045 models [21]

	Costs for 2030 reference model		
	Initial investment costs [M EUR/unit]	Lifespan [Years]	operating and maintenance costs expressed as a percentage of the initial investment
Onshore wind	1.08	30	1.25 %
Offshore wind	2.03	30	1.87 %
Photovoltaics (PV)	0.72	40	1.45 %
	Costs for 2045 reference model		

(continued on next page)

Should underground cavern storage prove unfeasible, the cost of hydrogen storage using alternative methods, such as metal–organic frameworks, would increase substantially. Additionally, this study uses water electrolysis for green hydrogen production. While electrolyser costs are expected to decrease significantly over time, green ammonia production via water electrolysis requires large volumes of water, posing particular challenges in arid regions. For this reason, exploring green hydrogen production through wastewater and biogas sources, potentially in combination with water electrolysis, is critical.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Hossein Asgharian: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Henrik Lund:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Investigation. **Jakob Zinck Thellufsen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology. **Florin Iov:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Mads Pagh Nielsen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Vincenzo Liso:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

Funding.

The authors acknowledge the financial support from HySTrAm project, Grant Agreement Number 101058643

(continued)

	Costs for 2030 reference model		
	Initial investment costs [M EUR/unit]	Lifespan [Years]	operating and maintenance costs expressed as a percentage of the initial investment
	Investment costs [M EUR/unit]	Lifetime [Years]	Fixed operating and maintenance in percentage of investment
Onshore wind	1.03	30	1.67 %
Offshore wind	1.90	30	2.51 %
PV	0.60	40	1.50 %

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] Sanchuli N, Dan S, Bagheri H. Ammonia application in cooling systems. *Prog Ammonia: Sci Technol Membr*, Elsevier 2024;113–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-88501-0-00004-5>.
- [2] Khudhur DA, Tuan Abdullah TA, Norazahar N. A review of safety issues and risk assessment of industrial ammonia refrigeration system. *ACS Chem Health & Saf* 2022;vol. 29, no. 5: p. 394–404. 10.1021/acs.chas.2c00041.
- [3] Afif A, Radenahmad N, Cheok Q, Shams S, Kim JH, Azad AK. Ammonia-fed fuel cells: a comprehensive review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2016;60:822–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.01.120>.
- [4] Zamfirescu C, Dincer I. Using ammonia as a sustainable fuel. *J Power Sources* 2008; 185(1):459–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2008.02.097>.
- [5] Erdemir D, Dincer I. A perspective on the use of ammonia as a clean fuel: Challenges and solutions. *Int J Energy Res* 2021;45(4):4827–34. <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.6232>.
- [6] Langella G, de Joannon M, Sabia P, Iodice P, Amoresano A. Ammonia as a fuel for internal combustion engines: latest advances and future challenges. *J Phys Conf Ser* 2022;2385(1):012036. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2385/1/012036>.
- [7] Chehade G, Dincer I. Progress in green ammonia production as potential carbon-free fuel. *Fuel* 2021;299:120845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2021.120845>.
- [8] Brandl A, Wawrzinek K. Provision of hydrogen and nitrogen for blue ammonia production at large scale. In Day 4 Thu, October 05, 2023, SPE; Oct. 2023. 10.2118/216889-MS.
- [9] Oh S, Mun H, Park J, Lee I. Techno-economic comparison of ammonia production processes under various carbon tax scenarios for the economic transition from grey to blue ammonia. *J Clean Prod* 2024;434:139909. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139909>.
- [10] Ali Khan MH, Daiyan R, Neal P, Haque N, MacGill I, Amal R. A framework for assessing economics of blue hydrogen production from steam methane reforming using carbon capture storage & utilisation. *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 46, no. 44, pp. 22685–22706, Jun. 2021. 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.04.104.
- [11] M. Proniewicz, K. Petela, A. Szlęk, and W. Adamczyk, “Life Cycle Assessment of Selected Ammonia Production Technologies From the Perspective of Ammonia as a Fuel for Heavy-Duty Vehicle,” *J Energy Resour Technol*, vol. 146, no. 3, Mar. 2024, 10.1115/1.4064371.
- [12] C. Smith and L. Torrente-Murciano, “Exceeding Single-Pass Equilibrium with Integrated Absorption Separation for Ammonia Synthesis Using Renewable Energy—Redefining the Haber-Bosch Loop,” *Adv Energy Mater*, vol. 11, no. 13, Apr. 2021, 10.1002/aenm.202003845.
- [13] Palys MJ, McCormick A, Cussler EL, Daoutidis P. Modeling and optimal design of absorbent enhanced ammonia synthesis. *Processes* 2018;6(7):91. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr6070091>.
- [14] Ishaq H, Shehzad MF, Crawford C. Transient modeling of a green ammonia production system to support sustainable development. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2023; 48(99):39254–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.07.036>.
- [15] Vinardell S, Nicolas P, Sastre AM, Cortina JL, Valderrama C. Sustainability assessment of green ammonia production to promote industrial decarbonization in Spain. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* 2023;11(44):15975–83. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscuschemeng.3c04694>.
- [16] Asgharian H, et al. The role of cryogenic carbon capture in future carbon-neutral societies. *Int J Greenhouse Gas Control* 2024;135:104161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jggc.2024.104161>.
- [17] Lund H, Thellufsen JZ, Østergaard PA, Sorknæs P, Skov IR, Mathiesen BV. EnergyPLAN – Advanced analysis of smart energy systems. *Smart Energy* 2021;1: 100007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segy.2021.100007>.
- [18] Ferrari S, Zagarella F, Caputo P, Bonomolo M. Assessment of tools for urban energy planning. *Energy* 2019;176:544–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.04.054>.
- [19] L. M. Pastore, G. Lo Basso, G. Ricciardi, and L. de Santoli, “Smart energy systems for renewable energy communities: A comparative analysis of power-to-X strategies for improving energy self-consumption,” *Energy*, vol. 280, p. 128205, Oct. 2023, 10.1016/j.energy.2023.128205.
- [20] “The Government’s strategy for POWER-TO-X.” [Online]. Available: https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/ptx/strategy_ptx.pdf.
- [21] “Technology Catalogues.” [Online]. Available: <https://ens.dk/en/our-services/technology-catalogues>.
- [22] Rivarolo M, Riveros-Godoy G, Magistri L, Massardo AF. Clean Hydrogen and Ammonia Synthesis in Paraguay from the Itaipu 14 GW Hydroelectric Plant. *ChemEngineering* 2019;3(4):87. <https://doi.org/10.3390/chemengineering3040087>.
- [23] H. Power, A. Milbrandt, and M. Mann, “Hydrogen Resource Assessment Hydrogen Potential from Coal, Natural Hydrogen Resource Assessment Hydrogen Potential from Coal, Natural Gas, Nuclear, and Hydro Power,” no. February, 2009.
- [24] Pruvost F, Cloete S, Arnaiz del Pozo C, Zaoubat A. Blue, green, and turquoise pathways for minimizing hydrogen production costs from steam methane reforming with CO2 capture. *Energy Convers Manag* 2022;274:116458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2022.116458>.
- [25] A. Ebrahimi, M. Meratizaman, H. Akbarpour Reyhani, O. Pourali, and M. Amidpour, “Energetic, exergetic and economic assessment of oxygen production from two columns cryogenic air separation unit,” *Energy*, vol. 90, pp. 1298–1316, Oct. 2015, 10.1016/j.energy.2015.06.083.
- [26] Lund H, et al. Smart energy Denmark. A consistent and detailed strategy for a fully decarbonized society. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;168:112777. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112777>.
- [27] Lund H, et al. The role of sustainable bioenergy in a fully decarbonised society. *Renew Energy* 2022;196:195–203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.06.026>.
- [28] Kany MS, et al. Energy efficient decarbonisation strategy for the Danish transport sector by 2045. *Smart Energy* 2022;5:100063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segy.2022.100063>.
- [29] “Energistatistik 2023;” 2023.
- [30] D. Connolly, “EnergyPLAN Cost Database,” no. January, pp. 0–15; 2012.
- [31] H. Asgharian, V. Pignataro, F. Iov, M. Pagh Nielsen, and V. Liso, “Exceeding equilibrium limitations: Enhanced temperature control for sustainable decentralized green ammonia production – a techno-economic analysis,” *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 315, p. 118764, Sep. 2024, 10.1016/j.enconman.2024.118764.
- [32] Adeli K, Nachtane M, Tarfaoui M, Faik A, Pollet BG, Saïfaoui D. Deep learning analysis of green ammonia synthesis: Evaluating techno-economic feasibility for sustainable production. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2024;87:1224–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.09.127>.
- [33] Fasihi M, Weiss R, Savolainen J, Breyer C. Global potential of green ammonia based on hybrid PV-wind power plants. *Appl Energy* 2021;294:116170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116170>.
- [34] “Statista.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1345797/forecast-global-ammonia-demand-by-application/>.
- [35] Asgharian H, et al. Techno-economic analysis of blue ammonia synthesis using cryogenic CO2 capture Process-A Danish case investigation. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2024;69:608–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.05.060>.
- [36] Biermann M, Normann F, Johnsson F, Hoballah R, Onarheim K. Capture of CO 2 from steam reformer flue gases using monoethanolamine: pilot plant validation and process design for partial capture. *Ind Eng Chem Res* 2022;61(38):14305–23. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.2c02205>.
- [37] Minougou JD, Gholami R, Andersen P. Underground hydrogen storage in caverns: Challenges of impure salt structures. *EarthSci Rev* 2023;247:104599. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2023.104599>.
- [38] Smith C, Hill AK, Torrente-Murciano L. Current and future role of Haber–Bosch ammonia in a carbon-free energy landscape. *Energy Environ Sci* 2020;13(2):331–44. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9EE02873K>.
- [39] Rouwenhorst KHR, Van der Ham AGJ, Mul G, Kersten SRA. Islanded ammonia power systems: Technology review & conceptual process design. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2019;114:109339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109339>.
- [40] Aneke M, Wang M. Potential for improving the energy efficiency of cryogenic air separation unit (ASU) using binary heat recovery cycles. *Appl Therm Eng* 2015;81: 223–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2015.02.034>.
- [41] Melaina M, Penev M. Hydrogen station cost estimates. *National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL)* 2013;no. September:1–36.
- [42] Danish Energy Agency. *Carbon capture, transport and storage: Technology descriptions and projections for long-term energy system planning*. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://ens.dk/en/our-services/technology-catalogues/technology-data-carbon-capture-transport-and-storage>.
- [43] Jensen M. Energy process enabled by cryogenic carbon capture,” BYU ScholarsArchive; 2015, [Online]. Available: <https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/etd>.